

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING TECHNOLOGY IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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Annotation: This article found out about the effectiveness of using technology in learning English. However, a few studies have shown that the students bring a strong potential to enhance language skills and promote the process of learning English quickly by technology.

Key words: technology, learning English, intellectual awareness, internet access, motivate students, social media.

It is no secret that technology has become more central in our daily lives than ever before. It helps us in every aspect of our lives, from health and fitness to creativity and social communication. The numerous students benefit from the online distance learning industry.

There has been a lot of research on using technology in learning English. Himmelsbach (2019) stated that when the internet is connected, we can access and collect information 24 hours a day. Moreover, we can find almost everything on the internet, with regularly updated versions. For students, this access helps find study materials and learn different skills and it opens resources from famous universities worldwide. Using technology in learning is an online world where learners use their image as their profile picture to immerse themselves in one place with various contexts. Secondly, life offers students a chance to connect and cooperate with other learners while away from classes. Furthermore, the learners can discover and communicate with other learners and immerse themselves in the language they are learning.

According to Zazulak (2016), one of the benefits of using technology in learning English is engaging students in new ways. We think using technology in learning especially smartphones are quite comfortable for today's youngsters. As all of the students try to find easy way of learning something, mobile phones and internet can be the best answer for their questions. According to Arifah (2014), accessing the internet will help motivate readers to learn. We can use pictures, films and music to increase their intellectual awareness and develop their thinking ability. Another benefit is that students can use English-related apps on their phones. We have noticed that traditional English learning methods are not interesting for modern humankind. Nowadays, people do not want to choose complicated way of learning something. For example, cadets can find a lot of useful information related to learning languages on the internet. Therefore, internet is one of the global sites of life for the time being.

According to Speck (2019), English language learners will benefit if they approach technology. Nowadays we are using technology in many different ways, especially in education. One of appropriate examples is some teachers of primary schools in Uzbekistan utilize English teaching methods through interesting videos or English related cartoons. Many scientists confirm that teaching using videos or cartoons is more effective than traditional methods. Hopkins (2017) said that people just knew something close to them in the past. However,

technology has changed all their minds. Now students can communicate with their friends, family and teachers immediately via smartphones. It is a very effective way of improving speaking and listening skills. Because they can communicate with friends in foreign countries. Especially they organize interview in English or other foreign languages. We have a chance for create new social media or communicate in exist social medias. For instance, there are some popular social medias such us Instagram, Twitter, Telegram and etc.

Moreover, Motteram (2014) claimed that the users such as teachers and students could access the internet to seek various information and debate with their classmates about what they have just found out in the world. Thanks to technology, especially the internet, learners can access to study efficiently. Learners can broaden their study extent when they have classes supported by technology.

According to Ahmadi (2018), technology makes learners study smoothly, but we should consider using it as a support tool in learning. There are several methods of teaching vocabulary using mobile phones or mobile applications. Furthermore, these things also accept learners to learn beyond the classroom. On the other hand, teaching activities will not restrict the places where students can take part with their lecturers and other students.

Computer technology and the Internet will use the benefits of studying through enhancing, rehearsing, and developing speaking skills. In this modern world, students can use some technology such as computer, tablets, and smartphones to access the Internet to communicate with foreigners and improve their language. However, there are some problems especially during Covid-19 pandemic, which spread worldwide, so many countries have been applying technology to learning, specifically in learning English. For instance, in Vietnam, there are a lot of schools, colleges, and universities that use technology in learning. However, many students and teachers have some difficulties using technology to learn English. For example, students and teachers hardly connect together, or teachers cannot motivate students because of traditional learning. Therefore, they do not want to use technology in learning.

On the other hand, using technology still has become more general, including learning English. The reason for using technology in learning English more widely is that it has many advantages. For instance, pronunciation will be improved by using pronunciation test apps. Communication skills also will be more proficient. In recent days, teachers of ESL are carrying out reforms in Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs. This academy trains cadets as a future lawyer. Therefore, cadets demand very different ways of teaching foreign languages. We are interested in psychological position of cadets and discovered some differences from university students. In fact, our Academy's rules do not allow using mobile or smartphones. However, there are opportunity to utilize internet access in information resource center by modern computers.

Based on the above mentioned facts one can conclusion that the role of technology in learning English is very grateful. All of the teachers are trying to utilize modern methods of teaching and its landing greatly effects of learning English for the time being. The effectiveness of using technology one of the best ways of learning English as a second language.

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